

Viruses	PDC n=14 (%)	INT-A n=14 (%)	HOS n=16 (%)
MERS (CVEMC)	S (100) N (71.4)	S (78.6) N (85.7)	S (100) N (87.5)
CVH22 (229E)	S (100) N (64.3)	S (92.8) N (64.2)	S (100) N (68.7)
CVHN1 (HKU1)	S (85.7) N (35.7)	S (78.6) N (28.6)	S (68.7) N (37.5)
CVHN2 (HKU1)	S (78.5) N (7.1)	S (85.7) N (28.5)	S (87.5) N (31.2)
CVHN5 (HKU5)	S (78.6) N (7.1)	S (85.7) N (28.6)	S (87.5) N (31.2)
CVHNL (NL63)	S (78.6) N (35.7)	S (78.6) N (50)	S (75) N (31.2)
CVHOC (OC43)	S (100) N (85.7)	S (100) N (57.1)	S (100) N (50)
CVHSA (SARS-CoV)	S (100) N (85.7)	S (92.8) N (71.4)	S (100) N (100)
SARS2 (SARS-CoV-2)	S (78.5) N (35.7)	S (64.3) N (50)	S (93.7) N (100)

Table 3. Percentage of individuals who developed IgG response against N and S proteins of the seven human coronaviruses in each patient group.